

Supplementary Material

**Structural characterization of the full-length anti-CD20 antibody
rituximab**

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Figure S1. Superposition between the machine learning (lilac and light red) and the homology modelling (cyan and dark red) predictions of the light chain (a), Fab portion heavy chain (b) and Fc portion heavy chain (c).

Figure S2. Scheme of the experimental data analysis integrated with computational modelling. Best model is obtained from SAXS data as a result of a procedure that uses experimental information in reciprocal (SAXS radial profiles) and direct (SAXS envelopes) space.

Figure S3. Logarithmic profile (a) and normalized Kratky plot (b) from SAXS measurements on rituximab. The position of the peak expected for compact globular scatters is shown by thin horizontal and vertical lines.

Table S1. Additives tested in solutions containing Rituximab.

Code	Extended name	IUPAC name	Properties
MPD	MPD	2-Methylpentane-2,4-diol	Surfactant and emulsion-stabilizer
ETO	EtOH	Ethanol	Alcohol naturally produced by the fermentation of sugars
BET	Betaine	(Trimethylazaniumyl)acetate	Amino acid derivative occurring in plants
SOB	Sorbitol	(2S,3R,4R,5R)-Hexane-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexol	Sugar alcohol
PRO	Proline	Pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid	Proteinogenic amino acid
TAU	Taurine	2-Aminoethane-1-sulfonic acid	Antioxidant, osmoregulator, membrane stabilizer
SAC	Saccharose	β -D-Fructofuranosyl α -D-glucopyranoside	Disaccharide
TWE	Polysorbate 80	Polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monooleate	Non-ionic surfactant and emulsifier

Table S2. Sugars of different complexity tested in solutions containing Rituximab.

Name	Type	Chemical formula	Chemical structure
Sorbitol	Monosaccharides	$C_6H_{14}O_6$	<p>The structure shows a six-carbon chain in a zig-zag conformation. Each carbon has a hydroxyl group attached. The hydroxyl groups on carbons 2, 3, and 4 are on the same side (pointing up), while the hydroxyl groups on carbons 1 and 5 are on the opposite side (pointing down). The terminal carbons (1 and 6) are bonded to hydroxymethyl groups.</p>
Glucose	Monosaccharides	$C_6H_{12}O_6$	<p>The structure shows a six-membered pyranose ring with an oxygen atom at the top. The hydroxyl groups are positioned as follows: C1 (right), C2 (left), C3 (right), C4 (left), and C5 (right). A hydroxymethyl group is attached to C6.</p>
Fructose	Monosaccharides	$C_6H_{12}O_6$	<p>The structure shows a five-membered furanose ring with an oxygen atom at the top. The hydroxyl groups are positioned as follows: C2 (right), C3 (left), and C4 (right). Hydroxymethyl groups are attached to C5 and C6.</p>
Galactose	Monosaccharides	$C_6H_{12}O_6$	<p>The structure shows a six-membered pyranose ring with an oxygen atom at the top. The hydroxyl groups are positioned as follows: C1 (right), C2 (right), C3 (left), C4 (left), and C5 (right). A hydroxymethyl group is attached to C6.</p>
Sucrose	Disaccharides	$C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$	<p>The structure shows two pyranose rings linked by an oxygen atom between their C1 and C2 positions. The left ring is an alpha-D-glucopyranose and the right ring is a beta-D-fructofuranose.</p>
Lactose	Disaccharides	$C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$	<p>The structure shows two pyranose rings linked by an oxygen atom between their C1 and C4 positions. The left ring is a beta-D-galactopyranose and the right ring is a D-glucopyranose.</p>
Maltose	Disaccharides	$C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$	<p>The structure shows two pyranose rings linked by an oxygen atom between their C1 and C4 positions. Both rings are D-glucopyranose.</p>
Cellobiose	Disaccharides	$C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$	<p>The structure shows two pyranose rings linked by an oxygen atom between their C1 and C4 positions. The left ring is a beta-D-glucopyranose and the right ring is a D-glucopyranose.</p>
Raffinose	Trisaccharides	$C_{18}H_{32}O_{16}$	<p>The structure shows three pyranose rings linked together. The leftmost ring is a beta-D-galactopyranose, the middle ring is a D-glucopyranose, and the rightmost ring is an alpha-D-glucopyranose. The entire structure is associated with five water molecules, indicated by $\cdot 5H_2O$.</p>

